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IBIDEM

per clarinetto e trombone

This is a handwritten musical score for Clarinet (Cl.) and Trombone (Tbn.). The score is written on three systems of staves. The top system features a Trombone staff with a 10-measure bracket and a Clarinet staff with a 5-measure bracket. The middle system includes a Trombone staff with a 5-measure bracket and a Clarinet staff with a 5-measure bracket, with the word "insieme" written above the Trombone staff. The bottom system contains a Trombone staff with a 5-measure bracket and a Clarinet staff with a 5-measure bracket. The score includes various musical notations such as notes, rests, and dynamic markings, along with graphical elements like triangles and lines indicating phrasing and articulation.

This image shows a handwritten musical score for Clarinet (Cl.) and Trombone (Trbn.). The score is written on three systems of staves, with the Clarinet part on the top staff and the Trombone part on the bottom staff of each system. The notation includes notes, rests, and various performance markings. Key annotations include:

- Cl. Part:** The first system has a bracket labeled "2nd max." above the staff. The second system has another "2nd max." bracket. The third system has a "T. 2nd max." annotation.
- Trbn. Part:** The second system has a "T. 2nd max." annotation. The third system has a "T. 2nd max." annotation.
- Graphical Elements:** There are several wavy lines and zig-zag lines drawn across the staves, possibly representing breath or articulation. A series of circles is drawn in the middle of the second system, with the word "scivolare" written below them.
- Other Markings:** There are various symbols, including triangles, circles, and arrows, scattered throughout the score, likely indicating specific performance techniques or dynamics.

Handwritten musical score for Clarinet (Cl.) and Trombone (Tbn.). The score is written on multiple staves, with the Clarinet part in the upper staves and the Trombone part in the lower staves. The notation is highly complex, featuring numerous slurs, dynamics markings (e.g., *2^a no. 2x.*, *3^a c.a.*), and various articulation marks. The staves are arranged in a non-linear fashion, with some staves overlapping or crossing each other. The music includes a variety of rhythmic patterns and melodic lines, with some staves showing a wavy, oscillating pattern. The overall style is that of a detailed, handwritten musical manuscript.

Handwritten musical score for Clarinet (Cl.) and Trombone (Tbn.). This section is more structured and rhythmic, featuring a series of notes and rests on the Clarinet staff and a corresponding bass line on the Trombone staff. The notation is simpler than the upper section, with clear rhythmic patterns and articulation marks. The staves are arranged in a linear fashion, with the Clarinet staff above the Trombone staff. The overall style is that of a detailed, handwritten musical manuscript.

Suggestions for musical performance

When the staff of each instrument merges into the other, a unique interpenetration between the two instruments takes place, both visually and acoustically: the individual viewpoints and ways of treating the sonic-musical event are abolished. Each performer will also find themselves acting within the other's "field", while still maintaining their own technical and mental grounding. The trombone used must be without an F-attachment, with one of the smallest bore sizes (approximately 1.39 cm).

Suggerimenti per l'esecuzione

Quando il rigo di ogni strumento si fonde nell'altro, si abbazza sia visivamente che acusticamente una compenetrazione unica fra i due strumenti: ormai le singole visioni e modi di trattare l'evento sonoro sono abolite. Ognuno si troverà anche nel campo d'azione dell'altro, mantenendolo sempre però le proprie acquisizioni tecniche e mentali. Il trombone usato dovrà essere senza ricotta, con un cannaeggio dei più piccoli (circa 1.39 cm.).

Segni The notation signs

(| |) attacco e andamento simultaneo simultaneous attack and motion

• suono più corto possibile play as short a sound as possible

• suono sostenuto fino al prossimo sound sustained until the next one

• suono sostenuto fino al prossimo con un lieve abbassamento o innalzamento () di intonazione prodotto esclusivamente da una minor pressione dell'aria sound sustained until the next one with a slight pitch dip or lift resulting from reduced air pressure

⊙ suono vocale prodotto nel bocchino come imitazione dell'altezza indicata vocal sound produced in the mouthpiece as an imitation of the indicated pitch

durata proporzionale
proportional duration

✕ pensare il suono fingendo di suonare to imagine the sound while pretending to play

☼ insufflando nello strumento senza produrre alcun suono, solo rumore di aria corrente blowing into the instrument without producing any sound, only the noise of the flowing air

☼ aspirare l'aria dello strumento con le labbra unite all'altezza indicata inhaling air through the instrument with the lips sealed, at the indicated pitch

☼ frullato flutter tonguing

— suono lungo fino ad esaurimento del fiato long sound sustained until the breath is exhausted

~~~~~ vibrato veloce rapid vibrato

~~~~~ vibrato a quarti di tono quarter-tone vibrato

⊖ allargare l'imbocatura verso un abbassamento di intonazione widen the embouchure to lower the pitch

⊕ tornare gradualmente alla posizione di emissione normale gradually return to the normal embouchure position

☼ muovere le coulisse come nel modello, producendo all'incirca nella posizione indicata colpi di aria brevi, senza risonanza sonora move the slide as indicated, producing short air bursts (no sound)

♯ mimesis = primo quarto di tono ascendente # trisisis = terzo quarto di tono ascendente ♭ mimesis = primo quarto di tono discendente

◁ crescendo ▷ diminuendo ◁▷ crescendo seguito da diminuendo ▷◁ diminuendo seguito da crescendo

◁▷ diminuendo fino a suono inudibile e viceversa. Le dinamiche si intendono comprese fra valori di intensità decisi dall'esecutore, comunque suggeriti dalle maggiore o minore ampiezze dei segni grafici

The dynamics are understood to lie within intensity levels determined by the performer, yet suggested by the greater or lesser amplitude of the graphic signs.

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